

A STUDY OF THE ADVANTAGES OF COOPETITION IN THE WOODWORKING INDUSTRY ENVIRONMENT IN MALAYSIA

LEE XIN YI

Fakulti Pengurusan Teknologi dan Teknousahawanan, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka, Malaysia.

MOHD FAZLI MOHD SAM*

Fakulti Pengurusan Teknologi dan Teknousahawanan, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka, Malaysia.

*Corresponding Author Email: mohd.fazli@utem.edu.my

LEE PEI YING

Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Perak, Malaysia.

Abstract

Coopetition can be characterized as a combination of cooperation and competition. The desire to increase their share of the alliance's revenue is shared by both the antagonistic parties. The purpose of this study was to examine the advantages of coopetition in the woodworking industry environment in Malaysia. The problem addressed in the study includes issues such as the availability of raw materials, labour shortages, shipping prices, and low productivity in the woodworking industry environment. To address these problems, the researcher conducted in-depth qualitative interviews with a purposive sample of nine owners or managers in the woodworking industry environment in Negeri Sembilan and Johor, Malaysia. The interview questions focused on the advantages. Microsoft Word was used for thematic analysis. Significant updates were implemented in data collection and analysis methods, the collection period, and data preparation steps. Findings, derived from multiple sources, presented participant profiles, characteristics, and a comprehensive analysis of statements. Out of nine participants, seven supported themes aligning with coopetition theory in the woodworking industry environment of Negeri Sembilan and Johor, while two participants held contrasting views. This highlights that these two participants did not endorse coopetition, believing competitors wouldn't collaborate and would always remain competitors. In conclusion, this study investigates coopetition dynamics in the woodworking industry environment in Gemas, Negeri Sembilan, and Segamat, Johor, Malaysia. Coopetitive advantages involve resource and order sharing, fostering mutual growth, profit increase with risk reduction, and optimizing market expansion. With insights gathered from interviews with nine participants, this research effectively fulfils its objectives, providing robust evidence of coopetition dynamics in the woodworking industry environment.

Keywords: Coopetition, Advantages, Woodworking Industry Environment, Malaysia.

1. INTRODUCTION

The woodworking industry environment is a broad and innovative field that includes many different types of crafts and professions. Carpenters, artisans, furniture builders, and woodworkers use wood to produce beautiful and useful items. The age-old craft of woodworking blends talent, imagination, and a respect for the natural beauty of timber (P-themes, 2023). Coopetition can be characterized as a combination of cooperation and competition. The desire to increase their share of the alliance's revenue is shared by both the antagonistic parties (Hamel, 1991; Zhang et al., 2020; Seepana et al., 2021). The main objective is to establish profitable relationships and increase value for both parties (Park and Kim, 2020; Nalebuff and Brandenburger, 1997). However, the idea of coopetition is not new. This method has been used for several years by businesses from

a variety of sectors to accomplish various strategic goals (Chai et al., 2020). For instance, International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) collaborated with Microsoft (Dowling et al., 1996; Kessler, 1998), Dell computers and IBM (Albert, 1999) in the information technology (IT) sector. Similar to this, Tesco and the Royal Bank of Scotland have a competitive relationship in the UK (Martinelli and Sparks, 2003). Apple and Google (Raza-Ullah et al., 2014) and Ritala and Huizingh (2014) both claim that Amazon and Apple have a cooperative-competitive partnership in the US.

The research is to study the advantages of collaborating with competitors in Malaysia's woodworking industry environment. This research also offers uniqueness in researching Malaysian woodworking industry environment because less research from previous paper on coepetition efforts among manufacturing companies. In the study, specifically selected Malaysia's woodworking industry environment because it has the potential to be transformed by coepetition forces due to the significantly increased demand for board products as materials to build homes, facilities, gardens, or animal boarding facilities.

The reason for choosing this article is that previous research in another country stated a few of advantages of working together with competitors in others industry, so that researcher have interested study it. There advantages of working together with competitors such as reducing financial risk, increasing the chance of gaining economic value, achieving innovation and internationalization, and solving the problems easily of working together with competitors in the woodworking industry environment.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this study, researcher recognise the problems discovered in the latest news about Malaysia's woodworking sector came from various sources. According to the "Malaysian Timber Industry Board aims to hit RM28 billion worth of timber exports by 2025," its chairman Datuk Hishamuddin Abdul Karim said. The news was found on Malay Mail Latest News and Headlines. (Malay Mail, 2022, September 22)

The Malaysian Timber Industry Board (MTIB), and the article was published on 2022. MITB will always place a high priority on empowering the growth of the nation's wood sector when dealing with current problems and challenges, such as those involving the availability of raw materials, labour shortages, shipping prices, and low productivity. Following the previous announcement of the 2022 Eastern Region Wood & Lifestyle Fair, MTIB spoke to the media to explain that it is now actively promoting the use of wood in the local market through advertising campaigns in the media, participation in exhibitions, and the organisation of exhibitions like the Wood & Lifestyle Fair, which it began branding in 2016.

According to Cygler, J., Sroka, W., Solesvik, M., & Dębkowska, K. (2018), the study had a number of limitations, the first of which was that it only examined one sector that took place in one nation. Moreover, they did not consider the partners' initial temporal orientation as we investigated the long-term impact of cooperative arrangements in this research. Future research could address this knowledge gap by examining how the duration of cooperative ventures impacts the outcomes of cooperative alliances for

partners with both short-term and long-term perspectives. Additionally, the researchers employed a quantitative technique previously, but future research may take a qualitative method to investigate the specific advantages of cooperative businesses. In this context, the researcher is uncertain whether employing a qualitative method would effectively solve these issues or provide insights into the advantages of cooperation in Malaysia's woodworking industry environment.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Concept of Coopetition

Coopetition, as defined by Bengtsson and Kock (2014), is a complex relationship where actors engage in simultaneous cooperation and competition, whether horizontally or vertically. This concept is strategically motivated, allowing both cooperation and competition to coexist without diminishing each other (Bengtsson et al., 2016). Coopetition spans multiple levels, including municipal, governmental, and organizational, and is a dynamic process influenced by evolving market conditions and objectives (Crick & Crick, 2019; Bouncken et al., 2015). It contributes to value creation and innovation (Bicen et al., 2021; Ritala, 2009) and often arises from the need to reduce costs and access complementary resources (Luo et al., 2007; Garaffo & Rocco, 2009). Cooperative alliances also carry high failure rates or may yield unsatisfactory outcomes (Dussauge et al., 2000; Bengtsson et al., 2020).

3.2 Historical of Woodworking Industry Environment in Malaysia

The Malaysian Investment Development Authority (2023) highlights that Malaysia is the world's leading exporter of wooden furniture and a major player in the global market for tropical wood and other wood products. Over the past two decades, Malaysia's economy has significantly benefited from the production of sawn timber, veneer, panel products (such as plywood, particleboard, chipboard, and fibreboard), mouldings, builder joinery and carpentry (BJC), as well as furniture and furniture components.

3.3 Overview of Woodworking Industry Environment in Malaysia

The export value of the country's timber products climbed by 3% in 2021 to RM22.74 billion from RM22.07 billion in 2020, according to Mail, M. (2022). The country's timber industry saw a 14% increase in exports between January and June of this year, reaching RM13.2 billion from RM11.6 billion during the same time in 2021.

The reason Malaysia was chosen as a research country is because, after the pandemic COVID-19, the demand for woodworking industry products was increasingly frequent, whether in Malaysia's domestic market or the international market, and the woodworking sector had the potential to gain a wider profit. Malaysia is in the top ten countries that produce and export furniture and furnishing, and its successes achieved a higher profit of RM10.41 billion. Malaysia exported the most to the following countries: The United States, Japan, Singapore, the United Kingdom, and Australia.

3.4 The Pioneer of Coopetition Research

The pioneer of written the coopetition research are Gary Hamel, Yves Doz, and C.K. Prahalad (1989), and this research created from Brighton, Massachusetts. Competition-related cooperation is appealing. The authors of this article provided a number of situations, including the manufacturing of automobiles by Toyota and General Motors, semiconductors by Siemens and Philips, photocopiers supplied to Kodak by Canon, and videocassette recorders made by Thomson in France and JVC in Japan. However, some people have expressed concern over the long-term repercussions of the expansion of what researchers refer to as "competitive collaboration"—joint ventures, outsourcing contracts, product licencing, and cooperative research. Strategic collaboration may reduce competition between the partners' businesses while strengthening both companies' barriers against external threats. It seems in particular that collaborations between Western rivals and Asian companies work against the Western partner. Collaboration offers new rivals a low-cost way to acquire access to technologies and markets.

3.5 The Advantages Working together with Competitors

3.5.1 Reducing Financial Risk

In prior research, collaborative financial risk assessment (CFRA) was used to mitigate financial risks. Traditional financial risk management faces challenges in risk identification and assessment, often ignoring business interconnectivity, long-term risk impacts, and the dynamic nature of risks. To address these gaps, the concept of collaborative open foresight—where organizations collectively discuss and analyze potential future developments—offers a promising approach (Gattringer et al., 2017). In CFRA, firms collaborate to identify and analyze financial risks, aiming to generate knowledge that enhances the chances of economic gains and reduces the likelihood of losses. This approach shifts from solely viewing risk negatively to recognizing risk as encompassing both potential threats and opportunities (Coleman, 2011). CFRA thus enables organizations to jointly manage financial risks with a forward-looking, dynamic approach.

3.5.2 Increasing the Chance of Gaining Economic Value

Recent research emphasizes the need for broader perspectives in risk governance to address complex and interconnected risks (Renn, 1998; Asselt & Renn, 2011). Traditional financial risk management often relies on historical data and short-term focuses, overlooking the interconnectedness of risk categories (Brunner-Kirchmair & Wiener, 2019). Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA) addresses these issues by allowing companies to anticipate and manage financial risks more proactively. CFRA brings together participants from varied backgrounds and organizations to collaboratively improve their understanding of financial risks, fostering broader insights and preparedness for future challenges. This approach not only reduces financial risk but also enhances potential economic gains by encouraging anticipatory, cross-organizational collaboration.

3.5.3 Achieving Innovation and Internationalization

Basterretxea, Charterina, and Landeta (2019) demonstrated that collectives of employees can enhance innovation and global reach through inter-cooperation, involving shared R&D units, joint sales offices, shared after-sales services, knowledge exchange, and the strategic relocation of key R&D technicians and managers. The close connections between cooperatives help mitigate risks of opportunistic behavior and information loss often associated with cooperation. The findings also suggest insights into the extent and conditions under which competitive strategies of cooperatives might be adapted to various ownership structures across different sectors.

3.5.4 Solving Problems Easily

Researchers have demonstrated how the role of cooperation within inter-firm relationships has changed over time in this research article, according to Zacharia, Z., Plasch, M., Mohan, U., and Gerschberger, M. (2019). This was done with a combination of social science theories, cooperation research literature, and empirical data from in-depth survey interviews. Customers' needs, organisational and European interconnection, and cooperation's three antecedents are present in most businesses and might encourage cooperation between competitors. Moreover, leaders should think about working with competitors to launch specific cooperation projects because cooperation has been shown to improve firm performance and interpersonal outcomes. This study has demonstrated that cooperation is an innovative sort of collaboration that firms should consider as they continue to successfully compete in a highly dynamic, uncertain, and chaotic market environment in the future. It is an effective inter-firm method to address problems quickly.

3.6 Conceptual Framework

The research framework outlines the steps to keep the study focused. Figure 1 presents the operational framework for this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3.7 Research Methodology

Numerous research methods can be used to gather rich data and in-depth knowledge of the area of study for case studies. The researcher employed both interviews and written materials for the purpose of this research. The respondents discussed the progress of the cooperative business partnership from a point of view of advantages during the interviews. There were a total number of nine owners or managers from the woodworking industries environment interviewed, with the locations being in Negeri Sembilan and Johor, Malaysia. Due to distance, 1 of the 9 personal interviews that were conducted was done over the phone. The interviews were conducted with those in positions of authority that are directly involved in the interactions between the woodworking businesses. In the study, the interviewer can be a general manager or director who served as an informant. Information from the intra-firm, inter-firm, and inter-individual levels could be gathered by interviewing persons in various positions within the organizations. The purposive sampling approach, a strategy used to choose the interviewer that have rich knowledge. According to Janesick (2000), the technique focuses on informants directing the researcher to further informants who could improve the current research. The interviews ranged in length from 10 to 45 minutes. All interviews were taped and written down. The researchers also gathered data from papers, such as meeting minutes from companies, in addition to conducting interviews. The interview transcripts and the materials were both analysed similarly when it came to empirical material analysis because they were both viewed as equally essential.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Result of Coopetitive advantages

Matrix coding query	Theme 1: Sharing resources and orders	Theme 2: Win-win and mutual growth	Theme 3: Profit increase and risk reduction	Theme 4: Market expansion and efficiency
Sources	6	3	2	4
Coding references	9	5	2	4

The study identifies key coopetition advantages in the woodworking industry environment. Six out of seven participants cited sharing resources and orders as the most common benefit, especially during challenges like incomplete orders or material shortages. Other advantages included profit increase and risk reduction (mentioned by two participants), and mutual growth (noted by three participants). Some participants also highlighted market expansion through collaboration. However, two participants felt that competition was too strong for cooperation, emphasizing self-interest over collaboration. Overall, coopetition offers significant benefits but remains challenging for some businesses.

4.1 Theme 1: Sharing Resources and Orders

The study identified several coopetition advantages in the woodworking industry environment based on interviews with nine participants. The most commonly reported

advantage, cited by six participants, was sharing resources and orders. This collaboration allowed businesses to manage challenges such as incomplete orders or material shortages, leading to more efficient operations means related with solving problems easily. For example, participants mentioned working together to fulfill large orders or share raw materials, which helped them complete tasks they could not manage individually. Theme 1: The section on achieving innovation and internationalization discusses the idea of "sharing resources and orders." The researcher identified "sharing resources and orders" as a key advantage of coepetition, which supports innovation and globalization, and solving problems easily. By collaborating, firms benefit from shared R&D facilities, joint sales and service efforts, expertise exchange, and the strategic relocation of personnel, reducing risks related to opportunistic behavior and information loss. Basterretxea, Charterina, and Landeta (2019) highlight how these strategies can enhance competitive advantages across various sectors and ownership structures through effective inter-cooperation.

4.2 Theme 2: Win-win and Mutual Growth

Furthermore, win-win and mutual growth, was acknowledged by three participants. They emphasized the importance of integrity in collaboration, where competitors share resources and information to ensure mutual benefits. For instance, Participant 2 (JP) discussed how sharing orders and maintaining good relationships with competitors can lead to long-term success, ensuring a steady flow of business for all parties involved. Theme 2: The section on "increasing the chance of gaining economic value" directly corresponds to the concept of "win-win and mutual growth" in the text. The section highlights that "win-win and mutual growth" can be achieved through strategies like Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA), which enables businesses to forecast and prepare for financial risks, thus enhancing economic value. CFRA involves collaboration among individuals from varied backgrounds to improve financial risk insights, aligning with the goal of mutual benefit. Brunner-Kirchmair and Wiener (2019) argue that traditional financial risk management lacks adaptability for complex, interconnected networks, whereas CFRA offers a proactive, innovative approach to manage future uncertainties and facilitate shared growth.

4.3 Theme 3: Profit Increase and Risk Reduction

Profit increase and risk reduction was another advantage highlighted by two participants. They noted that by collaborating with competitors, businesses could reduce risks and increase income, as the partnership allowed them to handle larger orders and share the financial burden. As Participant 4 (GFP) stated, "The income will naturally increase, and the risks will also decrease." Theme 3: "Reducing financial risk" aligns most closely with the concept of "profit increase and risk reduction" among the points identified by participants in the woodworking industry in Malaysia. The concept of "reducing financial risk" aligns with "profit increase and risk reduction," as observed by participants in Malaysia's woodworking industry. The section highlights the use of collaborative financial risk assessment (CFRA) as a proactive approach to mitigate financial risks, aimed at enhancing profitability while minimizing potential losses. This method addresses

limitations of traditional risk management, which often lacks adaptability and foresight. By incorporating collaborative and open foresight techniques, as outlined by Gattringer et al. (2017), CFRA allows businesses to dynamically assess financial risks within broader organizational challenges, promoting transparency and shared insight for future growth and risk reduction.

4.4 Theme 4: Market Expansion and Efficiency

Market expansion and efficiency emerged as another benefit, reported by three participants. They mentioned that by cooperating on larger orders or jointly developing new products, businesses could expand their market reach. Participant 1 (KLS) provided an example of two competitors collaborating on a research and development project that led to new eco-friendly products, increasing their market leadership. Theme 4: "Market expansion and efficiency" among the given points is also "increasing the chance of gaining economic value." The concept of "market expansion and efficiency" aligns with the idea of "increasing the chance of gaining economic value." The authors emphasize the importance of adopting a broader perspective in risk management to develop innovative strategies for managing risks and uncertainties in an interconnected world. They argue that traditional financial risk management methods often overlook these broader interactions, whereas Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA) enables companies to anticipate risks earlier, improving preparation and responsiveness. By expanding organizational boundaries and proactively preparing for future developments, CFRA enhances market understanding and operational efficiency, ultimately increasing economic value (Brunner-Kirchmair, T.M., and Wiener, M., 2019).

4.5 Reasons for Disagreeing with Coopetition

However, challenges in coopetition were also noted by two participants, Participant 5 (LBKE) and Participant 6 (JNP), who expressed skepticism about cooperation with competitors. They highlighted the difficulties in fostering cooperation due to the highly competitive nature of the industry, where businesses often prioritize self-interest over collaboration. Participant 5 (LBKE) explained, "Business is like this. Only businesses with no conflict can be friends."

Overall, while the majority of participants saw significant benefits in coopetition, some faced challenges in establishing collaborative relationships due to the competitive environment in the woodworking industry. These findings underscore the strategic value of coopetition, but also the complexities involved in balancing collaboration with competition.

5. CONCLUSION

The objective of this research is to study the advantages of collaborating with competitors in Malaysia's woodworking industry. Through readings and data collection, the researcher identified one of the advantages as sharing resources and orders. The section on achieving innovation and internationalization discusses the idea of "sharing resources and orders."

The writers of this section emphasize the ways in which groups of workers can benefit from collaboration in terms of innovation and globalization. These collaborations can include sharing R&D facilities, working together on joint sales and after-sale services, exchanging expertise, and relocating key R&D technicians and managers. To reduce the risk of opportunity-driven conduct and information loss, firms collaborate and share resources and orders. The idea of sharing resources and orders for mutual gain and strategic advantage is further emphasized by the focus on how cooperatives' competitive strategies can be implemented across sectors. In the pursuit of innovation and internationalization, Basterretxea, I., Charterina, and Landeta (2019) demonstrated the advantage that collectives of employees can gain through inter-cooperation.

This involves shared R&D units, joint sales offices, joint after-sale services, knowledge exchange, and the relocation of key R&D technicians and managers. The authors emphasize that the numerous connections and links among cooperatives help reduce the risk of opportunistic behavior and information loss associated with competition. The findings offer insights into the extent and conditions under which cooperative competitive strategies can be applied across different ownership structures and sectors.

The section on "increasing the chance of gaining economic value" directly corresponds to the concept of "win-win and mutual growth" in the text. The authors emphasize the necessity of adopting a more comprehensive approach to risk management and developing creative solutions for addressing complex potential hazards and uncertainties within interconnected networks. The introduction of Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA) is presented as a solution that allows businesses to forecast financial risks in advance, providing sufficient time for preparation.

The collaborative nature of CFRA involves individuals from diverse backgrounds working together to advance information that influences financial risk. The focus on creating economic value and reducing the likelihood of experiencing a loss aligns with the idea of a win-win scenario, where participating businesses benefit from each other's effective financial risk management and facilitate mutual growth. Recent studies underscore the importance of embracing a broader perspective in risk governance, emphasizing the need for innovative strategies to manage complexities in interconnected networks.

According to Brunner-Kirchmair, T.M., and Wiener, M. (2019), existing financial risk management approaches fall short in addressing these needs, relying on historical data and experience. They propose that Comprehensive Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA) offers a solution by allowing companies to forecast financial risks in advance, offering more time for preparation. CFRA, in conjunction with opening organizational boundaries and anticipating future developments, is seen as an effective approach to navigate upcoming challenges' complexity.

The article posits CFRA as a financial risk governance system that brings together individuals from diverse backgrounds to enhance knowledge and reduce financial risk, ultimately increasing the potential for economic value. The concept most closely resembling "market expansion and efficiency" among the given points is also "increasing the chance of gaining economic value." In this section, the authors discuss the value of

adopting a broader viewpoint in risk management to create novel strategies for handling complex potential risks and uncertainties in a highly interconnected world. Traditional approaches to financial risk management are criticized for not considering broader needs and interconnected networks. The authors suggest that Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA) can help companies forecast financial risks early, providing more time to prepare and find solutions. They propose combining the concepts of opening organizational boundaries and anticipatorily preparing for future developments to consider a wider view and more interactions. This aligns with the idea of increasing the chance of gaining economic value by expanding market understanding and enhancing operational efficiency through collaborative risk management strategies.

"Reducing financial risk" aligns most closely with the concept of "profit increase and risk reduction" among the points identified by participants in the woodworking industry in Malaysia. The section discusses the utilization of collaborative financial risk assessment to mitigate financial risk, as detailed by the authors. The primary objective of this collaborative approach is to generate future information facilitating an increased likelihood of economic value while reducing the chance of incurring a loss. This corresponds with the goal of minimizing financial risk to optimize the potential for profit growth. The collaborative and transparent foresight techniques emphasized in this section underscore the dynamic nature of risks and the interconnectedness of businesses, aiding in proactive identification and assessment of financial hazards. Consequently, the objective of achieving profit growth and risk reduction through collaborative financial risk assessment is directly associated with the "reducing financial risk" aspect. To address the deficiencies of traditional financial risk management, especially in risk identification and evaluation, the authors of the preceding research employed collaborative financial risk assessment. Traditional methods have been criticized for relying on fixed risk assessment techniques, overlooking long-term impacts, and neglecting the dynamic nature of organizations as open systems.

The authors advocate for the adoption of open and collaborative foresight methodologies to comprehensively identify and assess financial risks within the broader context of organizational hazards. Collaborative open foresight, as defined by Gattringer et al. (2017), involves an analysis and discussion process among organizations about future developments, focusing on relevant search fields and collectively considering issues related to individual strategies and innovation options for the future. It is deemed imperative to adapt open foresight elements to financial risk governance.

To sum up, this study highlights the various advantages of cooperation in Malaysia's woodworking industry. The exploration of cooperative strategies, such as sharing resources and orders, reveals advantages in terms of innovation, globalization, and risk reduction. The potential for creating economic value is further highlighted by the emphasis on "win-win and mutual growth" through the adoption of a more complete approach to risk management, especially with the advent of Collaborative Financial Risk Assessment (CFRA). The way that CFRA and the idea of "market expansion and efficiency" line up highlights how collaborative risk management may improve both market knowledge and operational efficiency. The article's suggestions for updating traditional financial risk

management, along with the participant-driven insights, highlight the significance of dynamic, open systems in tackling the interrelated problems facing the sector. All things considered, this study offers insightful viewpoints to companies looking for practical teamwork tactics to handle complexity, lower financial risk, and promote profit growth in the woodworking industry.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

The limitation of the research is the restricted number of participants available for interviews, restricting the researcher to engage solely with owners or managers in Malaysia's woodworking industries due to the qualitative methodology employed.

The recommendation for future research is expanding the study to include additional states across Malaysia is advisable, as it would provide a broader and more detailed understanding of the woodworking industry nationwide. While the current research focused on Johor, and Negeri Sembilan, extending it to multiple regions could yield a richer range of insights and enable valuable regional comparisons. However, to ensure a comprehensive analysis, it's important to consider that expanding the geographical scope may require extending the study's timeline.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledged the Sustainable Orange-Tech Life Value Excellence Research Group (SOLVE) research group of Center for Technopreneurship Development (C-TeD), the financial support through the publication incentive and the Fakulti Pengurusan Teknologi dan Teknousahawanan, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka. All errors and omissions are the responsibility of the authors.

References

- 1) Basterretxea, I., Charterina, J. and Landeta, J. (2019) 'Coopetition and innovation. Lessons from worker cooperatives in the Spanish machine tool industry,' *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 34(6), pp. 1223–1235. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jbim-01-2018-0015>.
- 2) Bouncken, R.B. *et al.* (2017) 'Coopetition in new product development alliances: Advantages and tensions for incremental and radical innovation,' *British Journal of Management*, 29(3), pp. 391–410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.12213>.
- 3) Brunner-Kirchmair, T.M. and Wiener, M. (2019) 'Knowledge is power – conceptualizing collaborative financial risk assessment,' *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 20(3), pp. 226–248. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrf-05-2018-0083>.
- 4) Chai, L. *et al.* (2019) 'The influences of interdependence, opportunism and technology uncertainty on interfirm coopetition,' *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 34(5), pp. 948–964. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jbim-07-2018-0208>.
- 5) Crick, J.M. (2019) 'Moderators affecting the relationship between coopetition and company performance,' *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 34(2), pp. 518–531. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jbim-03-2018-0102>.
- 6) Crick, J.M. (2020) 'Unpacking the relationship between a coopetition-oriented mindset and coopetition-oriented behaviours,' *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 36(3), pp. 400–419. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jbim-03-2020-0165>.

- 7) Cygler, J. *et al.* (2018) 'Benefits and Drawbacks of Coopetition: The roles of scope and durability in cooperative relationships,' *Sustainability*, 10(8), p. 2688. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082688>.
- 8) Köseoğlu, M.A. *et al.* (2018) 'The intellectual structure of coopetition: past, present and future,' *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 12(1), pp. 2–29. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jsma-07-2018-0073>.
- 9) Mail, M. (2022) 'Malaysian Timber Industry Board aims to hit RM28b worth of timber exports by 2025,' *Malay Mail*, 22 September. <https://www.malaymail.com/news/money/2022/09/22/malaysian-timber-industry-board-aims-to-hit-rm28b-worth-of-timber-exports-by-2025/29582>.
- 10) Mariani, M.M. and Belitski, M. (2022) 'The effect of coopetition intensity on first mover advantage and imitation in innovation related coopetition: Empirical evidence from UK firms,' *European Management Journal*, 41(5), pp. 779–791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2022.05.001>.
- 11) Niu, Y. *et al.* (2023) 'Coopetition configuration and performance of international joint ventures for high-speed rail projects,' *Engineering Construction & Architectural Management*, 31(9), pp. 3748–3772. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ecam-09-2022-0909>.
- 12) P-themes (2023). *Woodworking Industry - CECCORP*. [online] CECCORP. Available at: <https://ceccorp.ca/pages/woodworking-industry>.
- 13) 'Qualitative data gathering instruments and methods' (2021) in *Advances in library and information science (ALIS) book series*, pp. 77–98. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8549-8.ch004>.
- 14) *Sampling methods: types, techniques & best practices* (2024). <https://www.qualtrics.com/au/experience-management/research/sampling-methods/>.
- 15) Schiffing, S. *et al.* (2020) 'Coopetition in temporary contexts: examining swift trust and swift distrust in humanitarian operations,' *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 40(9), pp. 1449–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijopm-12-2019-0800>.
- 16) Shen, H. *et al.* (2021) 'The contingent effects of coopetition on new product development under dual institutional interactions: evidence from China,' *Chinese Management Studies*, 15(5), pp. 1104–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cms-10-2018-0726>.
- 17) Sin Chew Daily Malaysia (2022) '木材工业局放眼2025年 出口木制品达280亿 - 地方,' *星洲网 Sin Chew Daily Malaysia Latest News and Headlines*, 24 September. <https://www.sinchew.com.my/20220924/%e6%9c%a8%e6%9d%90%e5%b7%a5%e4%b8%9a%e5%b1%80%e6%94%be%e7%9c%bc2025%e5%b9%b4-%e5%87%ba%e5%8f%a3%e6%9c%a8%e5%88%b6%e5%93%81%e8%be%be280%e4%ba%bf/>.
- 18) Vătămănescu, E.-M. *et al.* (2021) 'Linking coopetition benefits and innovative performance within small and medium-sized enterprises networks: a strategic approach on knowledge sharing and direct collaboration,' *Kybernetes*, 51(7), pp. 2193–2214. <https://doi.org/10.1108/k-11-2020-0731>.
- 19) Virtanen, H. and Kock, S. (2022) 'Striking the right balance in tension management. The case of coopetition in small- and medium-sized firms,' *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 37(13), pp. 33–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jbim-10-2021-0469>.
- 20) Webb, T. *et al.* (2021) 'Growing the pie: an examination of coopetition benefits in the US lodging industry,' *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 33(12), pp. 4355–4372. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijchm-03-2021-0340>.
- 21) *Wood-Based and Furniture - MIDA | Malaysian Investment Development Authority* (2024). <https://www.mida.gov.my/industries/manufacturing/wood-based-and-furniture/>.
- 22) Zacharia, Z. *et al.* (2019) 'The emerging role of coopetition within inter-firm relationships,' *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 30(2), pp. 414–437. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijlm-02-2018-0021>.